

Deliverable D4.2

Report on IQS design and architecture

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101003750

Deliverable report

Deliverable No.	D4.2	Work Package No.	WP4	Task/s No.	Task 4.2
Work Package Title	Development of an integrated IoT/BIM/AI platform for smart quarrying [KTA4]				
Linked Task/s Title	ICT platform design and implementation				
Status	Draft	(Draft/Draft Final/Final)			
Dissemination level	PU	(PU-Public, PP, RE-Restricted, CO-Confidential)			
Due date deliverable	2023-11-30	Submission date	2023-11-30		
Deliverable version	DEQ_D4.2_AKKA_V3.0_20231130				

Document Contributors

Deliverable responsible	Akkodis	
Contributors	Organisation	
Sadeq Zougari	AKKODIS	
Benoit Dalet	AKKODIS	
Anne-Gaëlle Yar	AKKODIS	
Paul Marty	AKKODIS	
Prince-Eric Akmel	AKKODIS	
Reviewers	Organisation	
Diego LazaMartin	ABAUT	
Jesse Backman	METSO	
Paulo Romero	ANEFA	
Violeta Vazquez	ZABALA	
Eduardo García	ZABALA	

Document History

Version	Date	Comment
1.0	2023-11-02	Creation of the document, sent for external review
2.0	2023-11-20	Document updated to consider the reviewers' comments
3.0	2023-11-30	Final version
4.0	2024-03-01	Updated version after RP2 review: Executive summary updated with used tools. Missing physical units in screenshots added (34, 52, 53, 55, ...), Units added in the descriptions for Fig25-27, Typographical and language errors corrected.

	HMI design and colors: A final version of the Human-Machine Interface (HMI) ergonomics will be generated in the next deployment taking into account pilot sites needs.
--	--

Disclaimer

This document reflects only the author's view. Responsibility for the information and views expressed therein lies entirely with the authors. The European Commission are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

DIGIECOQUARRY project is fully concerned about the potential social risks that may arise as consequence of project's activities. For this reason, a dedicated Work Package (WP7 - Mechanisms for social acceptance & interaction with policy makers) is active since the beginning of the project identifying, analysing and monitoring social risks in each of the project sites. Main social risks have been already analysed and classified in deliverables 7.1 and 7.2, including also potential risks of DIGIECOQUARRY technologies' deployment beyond the end of the project. The identification and classification of social risks allows a close follow up of main potential negative impacts in society to avoid them along the whole project activities. Among potential social risks, impact in the workforce is monitored with specific attention to ensure full adaptation of workers to new working technologies and processes and avoid job destruction.

Withing the aim of WP4, it is important to consider the data collected from the workers to develop and validate advanced algorithms and models to optimize quarry processes and make them more sustainable. By taking into account the data collected, related to social risks and the quarry workers, we can develop more accurate and effective models that reflect the actual working conditions and ensure that the solutions implemented are adapted to their needs.

Table of contents

Deliverable report	2
Document Contributors	2
Document History	2
Disclaimer	4
Table of contents	5
List of Abbreviations	7
1 Executive Summary	9
2 Introduction	10
2.1 Concept/Approach	10
2.2 Deliverable objectives	10
2.3 Intended audience	10
3 Data flows between the expert systems of the quarries and the IQS	11
3.1 Cemex Data flow	12
3.2 Vicat Data flow	13
3.1 Holcim Data flow	14
3.2 Cimpor Data flow	15
3.3 CSI Data flow	16
4 IQS design and architecture	17
4.1 Data lakes	17
4.1.1 Components of the Data Lake	17
4.1.2 Interface with the IQS	20
4.2 IoT platform	51
4.3 Reporting and Management tools	53
4.3.1 Power BI ecosystem	53
4.3.2 Management tools	55
4.3.3 Power BI Dashboards deployment	74
4.4 IQS deployment diagram	74
5 IQS test plan	77
5.1 Test strategy	77
5.2 Test environment and tools	77
5.3 Methodology and process applied	78
5.3.1 Test preparation	78
5.3.2 Test execution	78

5.3.3	Test Results and test monitoring	78
6	Conclusions	80
7	References	82
	List of Figures	83
	List of Tables	85

List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
BI	Business Intelligence
BIM	Building Information Modelling
BMT	Business Management tools
CDE	Common Data Environment
CDMP	Centralized Data Management Platform for DEQ
CPU	Central Processing Unit
D2M	Drill-to-Mill
DEQ	DIGIECOQUARRY
DIU	Data Interface Unit
EDM	Environmental Data Management
EMT	Environmental Management Tool
EPD	Environmental Product Declaration
ES	Expert System
ETL	Extract Transform Load
GA	Grant Agreement
HDD	Hard Disk Drive
HMI	Human-Machine Interface
HTTPS	Hyper Text Transfer Protocol Secured
ICT	Information and communication technology
IoT	Internet of Things
IQS	Intelligent Quarrying System
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KSA	Key Social Area
KTA	Key Technology Area
LAN	Local Area Network
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
ML	Machine Learning
N/A or NA	Not applicable
Nb	Number

Abbreviation	Description
OS	Operating System
RDBMS	Relational Database Management System
REST-API	Representational State Transfer-API
SFTP	Secure File Transfer Protocol
SQL	Structured Query Language
SSD	Solid State Drive
VM	Virtual Machine
WP	Work Package
Unit	Description
€ / \$	Euro / Dollar
Go = Gb	Gibabyte
Ko = Kb	Kilobyte
Mo = Mb	Megabyte
Mn	Minutes
s	Seconds
To = Tb	Terabyte
File Format	Description
.csv (CSV)	Comma-separated values, delimited text file
.json (JSON)	JavaScript Object Notation, Data interchange format
.xml (XML)	Extensible Markup Language

1 Executive Summary

Digital Transformation in Quarrying Operations

The DigiEcoQuarry project represents a significant milestone in the realm of quarrying operations, fostering a digital transformation of traditional practices. The project revolves around the Intelligent Quarrying System (IQS), which serves as the central platform integrating various digital technologies, expert systems, and data sources to streamline operations, enhance efficiency, and provide data-driven insights.

The project's primary objective is to empower quarrying operations with advanced digital capabilities, thereby optimizing production, transport, improving environmental performance, ensuring safety, and promoting sustainable practices. The IQS incorporates a range of components, including a Data Lake platform, Internet of Things (IoT) infrastructure, expert systems, Business Information Modeling (BIM), Artificial Intelligence (AI) services, Data Warehouse, Power BI ecosystem, and Azure cloud services. These components create an ecosystem that transforms collected data into actionable insights.

Data Collection and Storage: The Foundation of IQS

One of the cornerstones of the project is the development of powerful data collection and storage infrastructure. Data sourced from sensors, expert systems, various databases, and automation systems are ingested and processed in the Data Lake. This foundational architecture ensures that a vast pool of valuable information is easily accessible for analysis, supporting the creation of a data warehouse system and enabling the extraction of key performance indicators (KPIs) across all quarrying aspects.

Microservices Architecture: Enhancing Agility and Scalability

The IQS embraces a microservices architecture that offers profound benefits. Microservices break down the system into modular, manageable components, enhancing agility, scalability, and fault tolerance. This approach streamlines development, maintenance, and updates, allowing for the rapid adaptation of services to evolving quarrying requirements. Microservices implementation relies on java Spring Boot Framework.

The IQS also emphasizes interfacing with external and diverse expert systems, enabling seamless data exchange with systems developed by partners, such as Abaut, Arco, DH&P, Maestro, Metso, Mintek and others. These interfaces are critical for sharing specific data related to various quarrying processes, such as crusher performance, crushing and screening optimization, automation, and control systems, mobile machinery performance thus enabling better data integration. Interfacing with expert system relies on proxies developed in Python or C#.

An integral focus of the project lies in the creation of robust reporting and management tools. These are complementary to existing ones provided by expert systems. The IQS leverages the Power BI ecosystem to create comprehensive dashboards and reports that provide insights into KPIs from different facets of quarrying. These tools break down data silos and facilitate data integration from diverse sources, enabling improved decision-making and performance tracking. IQS reporting relies on PowerBI.

Testing and Quality Assurance

The IQS implements a robust testing strategy and quality assurance framework. Testing activities encompass various environments, from unit tests on local PCs and integration in the cloud to validation tests in partner environments, ensuring that the system meets its specifications.

In conclusion, in 5 pilot environments, the DigiEcoQuarry project, designed and developed its Intelligent Quarrying System harnessing the power of digital technologies to provide integrated digitalized automatic process control for aggregates quarries.

2 Introduction

2.1 Concept/Approach

The D4.2 deliverable is the main output of the task 4.2, ICT platform design and implementation, run in the frame of the WP4, "Development of an integrated IoT/BIM/AI platform for smart quarrying [KTA4]", led by Akkodis, and involving the following other partners: VICAT, CEMEX, HOLCIM, CSI, CIMPOR, UPM-AI, APP and SIGMA.

Within this task 4.2, Akkodis organized several bilateral workshops with the involved partners (the pilot sites, SIGMA, UPM-AI and APP) to go deeply in the details of the ICT requirements specifically related to the Data Lake and to the IoT platform described within D4.1 deliverable. These workshops allowed Akkodis to gradually design and implement the data lake components and tools of the IQS to be used for the data generation/ingestion, the data storage and the data processing. Akkodis also designed, implemented, set up and configured an IoT platform. The description of the IQS design and architecture is presented in the next sections of this deliverable.

2.2 Deliverable objectives

The objectives of the D4.2 deliverable are to describe:

- The IQS data collection platform.
- The fundamental design principles followed in building the platform (scalability, reliability, security, and maintainability considerations).
- The different architectural components.
- The data flow managed within the IQS.
- The microservices architecture and the interfaces available for data exchange.

This deliverable also explains:

- The security principles which have been implemented.
- How the IQS is deployed within the Microsoft Azure infrastructure.

2.3 Intended audience

The dissemination level of this deliverable is public.

This deliverable is a key input for all the tasks to be done in the frame of the Task 4.5 of WP4 related to the ICT tools and services integration and deployment and mainly to the following tasks:

- Integration of the Expert Systems (ES).
- Integration of the BIM tools (refer also to D4.5 and D4.5.1).
- Integration of the AI based tools, including algorithms and data warehouse (refer to D4.4).
- Integration of the services developed by the project.

The partners involved in the other work packages such as WP2 (Selection and development of innovative aggregates processing techniques [KTA1, KTA2]), WP3 (Development of sensors, automation, and process control [KTA3]), WP5 (Development of integrated H&S [KTA5] and environmental systems [KTA6]) and WP6 (Pilot scenarios for quarrying operations monitoring [KSA7] & assessment [KSA8]), are also part of the intended audience of this deliverable as they are involved at least as data providers and/or data consumers for the IQS.

Any companies working in the mining industry and wishing to digitalize their business may also be interested in the content of this deliverable.

3 Data flows between the expert systems of the quarries and the IQS

Within the 5 pilot sites working in the frame of the DEQ project, some specific partners are involved according to the objectives defined for each of them (refer to the following sub-sections for details).

Some partners are involved for these 5 pilot sites such as Sigma/UPM-AI and APP that retrieve dataset from the quarries' data lakes respectively to implement some AI services and BIM solutions (refer to D4.1, D4.2 and D4.4 4.1.2.3.5 for details on Sigma/UPM-AI and APP's interactions with the DEQ data lakes).

Some data flows coming from the data lake could be processed by the data warehouse and by BIM solutions.

Chalmers and Roctim also retrieve from the 5 pilot sites' data lakes, on a monthly basis, the consumables, their allocations per module (i.e. process stage) and the tons produced by product (refer to D5.4). Then, they store EPD results and LCA reports generated by their PlantSmith tool.

Finally, the management tools can retrieve KPIs to propose business, environmental, transport and any other specific activity management dashboards.

All pilot sites can take advantage of their data lake by retrieving KPIs, reports and processed data which can bring added value for the management of their quarry.

The following sub-sections depict the data flows between these partners or systems within these pilot sites.

3.1 Cemex Data flow

The following diagram depicts the data flows within Cemex pilot site.

Figure 1: Cemex's Data Flow Diagram.

Cemex is the reference pilot site for the KTA1 (improved extraction, rock mass characterization and control) within Cemex's data lake, partners working on KTA1 can exchange data and results to facilitate their work and analysis related to the drill-to-mill (D2M) concept.

Cemex is also the reference pilot site for the KTA3.2 (monitoring sensors and analysing tools both for Mobile Machinery in Loading & Transport and for the recognition of workers) Abaut stores KPIs related to the mobile machinery fleet: usages, cycles, transportation times, distances, loading performance and transported tons (refer to D4.1 and to the section 4.1.2.3.5 for details on Abaut's interactions with the DEQ data lakes).

3.2 Vicat Data flow

The following diagram depicts the data flows within Vicat pilot site.

Figure 2: Vicat's Data Flow Diagram.

Vicat is the reference pilot site for the KTA2.1 (innovative mobile crusher) within this data lake, Vicat and Metso can exchange and analyze data and results to reach their objectives related to the optimization of the treatment of the recycled materials (reduce dust and noise emission, reduce energy and fuel consumption...) (refer to D4.1 and to the section 4.1.2.3.1 for details on Metso's interactions with this data lake).

Abaut also contributes to these Vicat's objectives by producing images enabling a better analysis of the incoming recycled raw materials. These images can be stored in Vicat's data lake (refer to D4.1 and to section 4.1.2.3.5 for details on Abaut's interactions with the DEQ data lakes).

At last, Arco is also involved on this pilot site; Arco stores the tons produced thanks to the implementation of its weighing system (refer to D4.1 and to section 4.1.2.3.4 for details on Arco's interactions with the DEQ data lakes).

3.3 Holcim Data flow

The following diagram depicts the data flows within Holcim pilot site.

Figure 3: Holcim's Data Flow Diagram.

Holcim is the reference pilot site for the KTA3.1 (production control system and automation) Here, Maestro has implemented a SCADA system that generates production data shared within this data lake (this shared data includes also some data related to the tons produced generated by Arco's expert system) (refer to D4.1 and to the section 4.1.2.3.3 for details on Maestro's interactions with the Holcim's data lake)

As the reference pilot site also for the KTA2.2 (models for crushing and screening optimization) Holcim exchanges data and results with Mintek. This facilitates their tasks of analysis that aim at improving the efficiency of the crushing stage of the treatment plant process (reduce noise, reduce energy consumption etc....) (refer to D4.1 and to the section 4.1.2.3.2 for details on Mintek's interactions with the Holcim's data lake)

Abaut is also involved in Holcim pilot site. Abaut produces and stores in the Holcim's data lake, images useful for a better recognition for workers nearby the mobile machineries (refer to D4.1 and to the section 4.1.2.3.5 for details on Abaut's interactions with the DEQ data lakes)

3.4 Cimpor Data flow

The following diagram depicts the data flows within Cimpor pilot site.

Figure 4: Agrepor Cimpor's Data Flow Diagram

Cimpor is the reference pilot site for the KTA3.1 (packaging optimization, automation software and electrical connections) Here, Arco has implemented a weighing system that generates production data shared within this data lake (refer to D4.1 and to the section 4.1.2.3.4 for details on Arco's interactions with the DEQ data lakes).

Cimpor is also the reference pilot site for the KTA3.2 (monitoring sensors and analysing tools, for external transport) About stores KPIs related to the mobile machineries: usages, cycles, transportation times, distances, loading performance and transported tons (refer to D4.1 and to the section 4.1.2.3.5 for details on About's interactions with the DEQ data lakes).

3.5 CSI Data flow

The following diagram depicts the data flows within CSI pilot site.

Figure 5: CSI's Data Flow Diagram

CSI is the reference pilot site for the KTA3.3 (mobile equipment digitalisation, real time modelling & data collection and geofence) Here, DH&P stores data and KPIs related to the CSI's mobile machineries: asset parameters and values, loading performance and transported tons (refer to D4.1 and to the section 4.1.2.3.64.1.2.3.5 for details on DH&P's interactions with the CSI data lake) The analysis of this data and KPIs by CSI is designed to help them reach their objectives for reducing fuel consumption, CO2 emissions and transport distances.

4 IQS design and architecture

4.1 Data lakes

4.1.1 Components of the Data Lake

Developing the data lakes part of the IQS consisted in designing and implementing tools or components for:

- data generation / ingestion.
- data storage.
- data processing.

Here is a global view of the components that are used to build the IQS data lakes:

Figure 6: Data Lake architecture components view.

Below, you will find specific details provided for each component.

4.1.1.1 Application Gateway or Swagger Interface

Figure 7 Frontal Gateway

The application gateway is the Frontal Gateway of DigiEcoQuarry Application. It exposes specific REST API Web Services (see schema above) whose input data are processed by dedicated micro-services. The Swagger interface presents all existing Rest API operations and their documentation and allows developers to invoke them directly. When deployed in a production mode, the Gateway integrates high availability, load balancing and a firewall.

4.1.1.2 Keycloak

Figure 8 Keycloak

Keycloak¹ is an open-source solution for authenticating and authorizing users who request applications and services.

Keycloak is an Identity and Access Management (IAM) which:

- Implements OpenID Connect in IQS context.
- Uses the external database PostgreSQL to manage Users and Roles.

Factually, Keycloak offers HMIs to enter some fundamental concepts as:

- Users, User Groups and Roles.
- Applicative Resources to be authenticated and Applicative Rights to access Applicative Resources.

After entering the fundamentals (the provisioning),

- Users are gathered into User Groups.
- Applicative Rights are gathered into Roles.
- Roles are assigned to User Groups.

Technically, a token exchange between DEQ Clients and the Keycloak server is implemented when a client tries to access the web application or directly a REST resource managed by the web application; this implementation is "natively" assured by Keycloak using OpenID Connect. Note that this OpenID Connect implementation is strongly secured.

This architecture, including many open-source components will significantly reduce the operating costs, will provide the most flexible architecture and the most reversible solution, but will generate additional development costs.

Note that these additional costs would remain the same with the couple solution AAD (Azure Active Directory) / ADDS (Azure Active Directory Domain Services) which needs a strong high-level configuration to be implemented and above all secured (by Kerberos for example).

Keycloak might be deployed on the same Talend VM to reduce costs.

PostgreSQL database is used as Keycloak internal database.

¹ <https://www.keycloak.org/>

4.1.1.3 Microservices

Figure 9 Microservices

Microservice-based architecture is highly adopted to implement different services. All these microservices could be deployed on the same Talend VM to reduce costs.

Download and upload microservices are generic microservices that drop down or retrieve files from the BLOB storage of the Data Lake.

Data restitution and data ingestion microservices are presented as generic in the schema for convenience but are dedicated to the data involved by the User request: for example, when a Partner activates a data ingestion request, the RESTful API requested is dedicated to this Partner; each Partner has its own data ingestion microservice.

A such microservice:

- Retrieves an input archive file (containing data files + a metadata file).
- Performs the same tasks as an upload microservice (drop down files into dedicated containers of the BLOB storage).
- Parses the files to extract raw data.
- Stores the raw data into tables of dedicated PostgreSQL databases.

This architecture including many open-source components will significantly reduce the operating costs and will provide the most flexible architecture and the most reversible solution. However, it can generate additional development costs. Note nevertheless that development costs would not be lower if Azure components (as Azure Logic Apps or App Service solution) were used.

4.1.1.4 Talend (ETL tool)

Figure 10 Talend ETL tool

Talend OS ESB (Open Studio Enterprise Server Bus) is used for development. Talend runtime is deployed over a dedicated Azure VM. Talend OS ESB:

- Performs Extraction, Transformation, Loading of large data sets.
- provides trigger connectors when REST API or HTTP Requests are consumed and any other connectors to connect any storages.

Especially in DEQ context, Talend:

- Reads PostgreSQL Databases and extracts data.
- Generates specific contents with the retrieved data, used to enrich incoming data.

Talend processes are organized into multiple pipelines, each of which is scheduled for regular execution or triggered after an upload operation. These pipelines generate essential outputs required by the business management tools.

4.1.1.5 Special process

Figure 11 File Dropper

File Dropper process is executed asynchronously and awakened every (customizable) n minutes.

It performs the following tasks:

- It retrieves files previously uploaded in a specific upload directory hosted in the File System.
- It drops down files into containers of Azure BLOB Storage, dedicated to Site process or partners tasks according to directives based on the file nomenclature and its related metadata.
- If necessary, it can call some other process which ingest data extracted from the uploaded files, into dedicated databases.

Data Ingestor process ingests data into specific databases. It is used because some Partners or Sites data need to be stored not only in BLOB Storage as incoming files, but also as incoming granular data to be treated later for computing KPIs.

Data Ingestor process performs the following tasks:

- It parses uploaded files to extract data.
- It stores the extracted data into mirror-tables of specific databases.

4.1.1.6 Azure Data Storage, PostgreSQL (Storage tools)

Figure 12 Azure Data Storage

IQS data files are stored by microservices within dedicated Azure blob storage containers.

Detailed specifications have determined that a NoSQL database is not required for this project, and PostgreSQL has been chosen as the preferred hierarchical database solution.

4.1.2 Interface with the IQS

4.1.2.1 Centralized Data management Platform (CDMP) and tools

The CDMP is a centralised platform developed by AKKODIS using open-source frameworks. It aims to collect and store data from the Pilot Sites, and allows IQS and quarry partners to browse, access and download data. The data are associated with metadata -data description-, stored in a database, used to fetch, and retrieve data. Data itself is stored in a data lake.

Uploading, browsing, accessing, and downloading data can be done using REST APIs provided by the CDMP.

Figure 13: CDMP general architecture.

Data is uploaded to CDMP along with metadata, an accurate and complete description of the data, formalized in an XML description file. A common description model has been agreed between partners, based on Pilot Site, processes, etc.

This metadata, stored in a dedicated database, is used to organize data in the data lake containers and databases, and later to browse and retrieve data. The data lake containers and databases are created following data models defined by data providers, enabling cross access to data coming from different processes. Access to data lake containers is granted following an authorization policy defined by pilot site and partners.

The CDMP provides a web interface enabling access to uploaded data, and data sharing between partners of pilot sites according to authorizations defined by pilot site.

For specific needs, and usage not covered by CDMP mechanism, pilot sites and partners can use directly low-level data lake API to take advantage of data lake features.

4.1.2.1.1 CDMP Front-End

Each pilot site has its own CDMP Front-End according to its needs.

Figure 14: CDMP Front-End: Welcome page – “Home” screen.

4.1.2.1.1.1 Shared data

Actions	ID	Quarry Process	Sub Process	Sharing Description	Sharing Item Description	Sharing Date
<input type="checkbox"/>	934	BIM	3D BIM Model	An IFC file is a model file created in the Industry Foundation Classes format. It contains a building or facility model, including spatial elements, materials, and shapes.	Hanson 3D BIM Model Testing Purpose	26/06/2023
<input type="checkbox"/>	933	Treatment and Storage (TAS) 1	Automation-Process Control	This file contains daily production data.	2023-04-17 Production Data	17/04/2023
<input type="checkbox"/>	932	Treatment and Storage (TAS) 1	Automation-Process Control	This file contains daily production data.	2023-04-18 Production Data	18/04/2023
<input type="checkbox"/>	931	Treatment and Storage (TAS) 1	Automation-Process Control	This file contains daily production data.	2023-04-20 Production Data	20/04/2023
<input type="checkbox"/>	930	Treatment and Storage (TAS) 1	Automation-Process Control	This file contains daily production data.	2023-04-19 Production Data	19/04/2023
<input type="checkbox"/>	929	Treatment and Storage (TAS) 1	Automation-Process Control	These files contain the SCADA data of HOLLIM.	2023-04-10 Production Data	10/04/2023
<input type="checkbox"/>	928	Treatment and Storage (TAS) 1	Automation-Process Control	These files contain the SCADA data of HOLLIM.	2023-04-09 Production Data	06/04/2023
<input type="checkbox"/>	927	Treatment and Storage (TAS) 1	Automation-Process Control	These files contain the SCADA data of HOLLIM.	2023-04-05 Production Data	05/04/2023
<input type="checkbox"/>	926	Treatment and Storage (TAS) 1	Automation-Process Control	These files contain the SCADA data of HOLLIM.	2023-04-12 Production Data	12/04/2023
<input type="checkbox"/>	925	Treatment and Storage (TAS) 1	Automation-Process Control	These files contain the SCADA data of HOLLIM.	2023-04-04 Production Data	04/04/2023

Figure 15: CDMP Front-End – “Shared Data” screen.

The “Shared Data” HMI displays the list of the zip files (archives) which are uploaded into the pilot site’s CDMP with their main metadata information (ID, Quarry_Process, Sub_Process, Sharing_Description, Sharing_Item Description, Sharing_Date).

The IQS user can sort and filter this list according to this different data. The user can also perform the following actions:

- Select one or several uploaded zip files and then download all the selected zip files.

Download selected

Here the user can still unselect specific zip files and refine its list by filtering on any displayed data before confirming the download of the selected items.

Summary of selected Items

Actions	ID	Quarry Process	Sub Process	Sharing Description	Sharing Item Description	Sharing Date
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	1	Environment and Energy (KTA6)	Environment and Energy	This file represents EPD-M1 and LCA_Results	test files for AGREPOR-CIMPOR	2023-01-11
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	2	Loading and Hauling (Internal Transport) and External Transport (KTA3.2)	Loading and Hauling	ABAUT	String	2023-01-16
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	4	Loading and Hauling (Internal Transport) and External Transport (KTA3.2)	Loading and Hauling	ABAUT	String	2023-01-17

Items per page: 5 | 1 - 3 of 3 | < >

Cancel | Confirm download

Figure 16: CDMP Front-End – “Summary of selected Items”(Shared data) screen.

i Display all the information related to the uploaded zip file:

1 - Details

ID	Quarry Process	Sub Process
1	Loading and Hauling (Internal Transport) and External Transport (KTA3.2)	Loading and Hauling
Sharing Description	Sharing Item Description	Sharing Date
about		2022-10-27

Figure 17: CDMP Front-End – “Details” (Shared data) screen.

Download each uploaded zip file.

Consult the list of the files available in each uploaded zip file:

1 - Files Available ×

Actions	Filename	Type	Log Station ID	Format	Comment
	20200812_AT00...	DataSet	0	CSV	String
	20200812_AT00...	DataSet	0	CSV	String
	20200812_AT00...	DataSet	0	CSV	String
	20200812_AT00...	DataSet	0	CSV	String
	metadata_descri...	XSD		XML	Metadata Desc...

1 to 5 of 5 < < Page 1 of 1 > >

Figure 18: CDMP Front-End – “Files available” (Shared data) screen.

For each file, following information is shown in this screen:

- Filename.
- Type.
- Log Station ID.
- Format.
- Comment.

The IQS user can filter and download each file. Besides, metadata can be used for automatic data retrieval using dedicated Rest API.

4.1.2.1.1.2 Sharing data process monitoring

Figure 19: CDMP Front-End – “Shared Data Task” screen.

The “Shared Data Task” HMI displays the list of the upload tasks executed into the pilot site’s CDMP. For each task, a list of metadata is shown in this screen to track the execution of the tasks.

4.1.2.1.1.3 Talend process monitoring

Figure 20: CDMP Front-End – “Talend Process” screen.

The “Talend Process” HMI displays the list of the tasks executed by Talend after some specific upload tasks executed into the pilot site’s CDMP. For each Talend task, a list of metadata is shown in this screen to track the execution of the tasks.

4.1.2.1.1.4 Data lake browser tool

Akkodis developed new services at CDMP level to browse the data lake: the “Data lake browser” tool. This tool is a dynamic catalogue that provide access to data shared by external system (IoT). The functions are:

- Data lake browser container management (creation and deletion).

- Data lake browser visualization.
- Data lake content search and download (simple and advanced search).
- Data lake content search REST APIs.
- Automatic synchronization of the Data lake and the IQS.

Figure 21: CDMP Front-End – “Data lake Browser” screen.

The “Data lake Browser” HMI displays the list of the data shared by external system (IoT). For each row a list of metadata describes each file (Name, Path, LastModified date, ContentType, ContentLength, Container, Metadata).

The IQS user can sort and filter this list according to this different data. The user can also perform the following actions:

- Select one or several shared data and then download all the selected shared data.

Download selected

Here the user can still unselect specific shared data and refine its list by filtering on any displayed data before confirming the download of the selected items. Note that the “Total size” of the selected shared data is displayed to inform the user and avoid a too huge/long download.

Summary of selected Items

Filter

Actions	Id	Name	Path	LastModified	ContentType	Content
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	12663	15.avro	iothub-nbzeycznnq3os/01/2023/10/23/04/15.avro	2023-10-23T04:17:01Z	application/octet-stream	2 KB
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	12664	15.json	iothub-nbzeycznnq3os/01/2023/10/23/04/15.json	2023-10-23T04:17:01Z	application/octet-stream	2 KB
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	5224	08.json	iothub-nbzeycznnq3os/00/2023/10/23/04/08.json	2023-10-23T04:10:03Z	application/octet-stream	2 KB

Items per page: 5 | 1 - 3 of 3 | < >

Total size: 6KB

Cancel Confirm download

Figure 22: CDMP Front-End – “Summary of selected items”(Data lake Browser) screen.

i Display all the information related to the shared data:

12663 - Details

Id 12663	Name 15.avro	Path iothub-nbzeycznnq3os/01/2023/10/23/04/15.avro
LastModified 2023-10-23T04:17:01Z	ContentType application/octet-stream	ContentLength 2 KB
Container sigma-ent	Metadata PartitionEpoch: {“DataLossNumber”:133328696 134516132,“ConfigurationVersion”:68719476736,“GenerationNumber”:0}	

Figure 23: CDMP Front-End – “Details”(Data lake Browser) screen.

Download each shared data.

Delete each shared data.

The user can also:

Refresh data refresh the list of the shared data from stored in the database.

Fetch Data refresh the list of the shared data from stored in the database by parsing all the registered data lake containers.

4.1.2.1.1.5 Plant Production

Actions	ID	Product Type	Product Name	Date	Production Start	Production End	Down Time	Production Mass	Consented Time	Total Time
	882	Frantumati	0/4	19/10/2023	08:04:49	17:33:41	0	0	14	12
	883	Frantumati	4/6	19/10/2023	08:10:53	16:57:41	0	0	14	12
	884	Frantumati	6/12	19/10/2023	01:00:00	01:00:00	0	0	14	12
	885	Frantumati	12/22	19/10/2023	01:00:00	01:00:00	0	0	14	12
	886	Naturali	0/4	19/10/2023	01:00:00	01:00:00	0	0.155	14	12
	887	Naturali	0/8	19/10/2023	01:00:00	01:00:00	0	762.564	14	12
	888	Naturali	8/15	19/10/2023	01:00:00	01:00:00	0	213.738	14	12
	889	Naturali	15/22	19/10/2023	01:00:00	01:00:00	0	243.016	14	12

Figure 24: CDMP Front-End – “Plant Production” screen

The “Plant Production” HMI displays the list of the daily plant production data by product which are uploaded into the pilot site’s CDMP. For each daily plant production data of a given product, following information is shown in this screen:

- ID
- Product Type*
- Product Name*
- Production Date*
- Production Start Time (optional)
- Production End Time (optional)
- Production Mass* (t)
- Consented Time* (h)
- Total Time* (h)
- Planned Maintenance Time* (h)
- Downtime* (h)
- Under Load Time* (h)
- Lack of Feed Time* (h)
- Capacity* (t/h)
- Scheduled Hours (h)
- Operating time (h)

- Real Production time (h)
- Net Time (h)
- Average Actual Rate (t/h)

Minimum data are indicated with a star (*), other data are automatically calculated.

The IQS user can sort and filter this list according to this different data.

In rare cases, the two manual actions (add, update) will allow the user to create or update system data in order to enable the consolidation of production data.

4.1.2.1.1.6 Plant Consumption

Actions	ID	ConsumptionDate	Fuel	Diesel	Energy	WaterUsedForMiningWorks	PrimaryFreshWater	RecycledWater	TotalProducedTons	TotalWater	FuelConsumptionPerTonProcessed
✓	1450	01/02/2023	103	88	881	709	863	250	2744	1822	0.037536442
✓	1451	02/02/2023	69	100	6412	487	907	352	2728	1746	0.025262355
✓	1452	03/02/2023	56	128	12079	402	574	314	1974	1290	0.028368793
✓	1453	06/02/2023	52	139	11414	214	527	369	1257	1110	0.041368335
✓	1454	07/02/2023	117	50	2335	198	652	245	4289	1095	0.027279086
✓	1455	08/02/2023	59	100	6157	312	150	261	3527	723	0.016728098
✓	1456	09/02/2023	100	123	4956	761	586	305	1618	1632	0.061804697
✓	1457	10/02/2023	60	106	5859	512	616	309	4287	1437	0.013995801
✓	1458	13/02/2023	63	83	14834	403	729	218	2671	1350	0.023586672
✓	1459	14/02/2023	65	123	4470	305	406	200	2345	911	0.02771855

Figure 25: CDMP Front-End – “Plant Consumption” screen

The “Plant Consumption” HMI displays the list of the daily plant consumption data which are uploaded into the pilot site’s CDMP. For each daily plant consumption data, following information is shown in this screen:

- ID.
- Consumption Date*.
- Fuel*. (l)
- Diesel*. (l)
- Energy*. (kWh)
- Water used for Mining works*. (m3)
- Primary Fresh Water*. (m3)
- Recycled Water*. (m3)
- Total Water. (m3)
- Total Produced tons*. (t)
- Fuel Consumption per ton processed. (l/t)
- Diesel Consumption per ton processed. (l/t)
- Energy consumption per ton processed. (kWh/t)
- Total Water consumption per ton processed. (m3/t)

Minimum data are indicated with a star (*), other data are automatically calculated.

The IQS user can sort and filter this list according to this different data.

In rare cases, manual actions (add, update) will allow the user to create or update system data in order to enable the consolidation of consumption data.

4.1.2.1.1.7 REE (Running Equipment Effectiveness)

Actions	Id	SaleDate	BestDemonstratedPractice	ProductType	SaleableAggregateProductName	SaleableAggregateProcessed	ActualOperationTimeAverage	LackOfFeedTimeAverage	RunningTimeAverage
	1254	01/02/2023	500	Naturali	0/4	3487	12	1.2307693	10.461538
	1255	02/02/2023	500	Frantumati	6/12	743	12	1.1666666	10.166667
	1256	03/02/2023	500	Naturali	0/4	534	12	1.3076923	10.384615
	1257	06/02/2023	500	Frantumati	4/6	2889	12	0.85714287	9.714286
	1258	07/02/2023	500	Naturali	8/15	794	12	1.8571428	10.285714
	1259	08/02/2023	500	Frantumati	12/22	712	12	1.7142857	9.285714
	1260	09/02/2023	500	Naturali	15/22	3576	12	1.1666666	9.166667
	1261	10/02/2023	500	Frantumati	0/4	943	12	1.4	9.8
	1262	13/02/2023	500	Naturali	0/6	796	12	2	10.6
	1263	14/02/2023	500	Frantumati	6/12	965	12	1.4363636	10.272727

Figure 26: CDMP Front-End – “REE” screen (Running Equipment Effectiveness)

The “REE” (Running Equipment Effectiveness) HMI displays the list of the daily sales by product which are uploaded into the pilot site’s CDMP. For each daily sales data, following information is shown in this screen:

- ID.
- Sale Date*.
- Best Demonstrated Practice*. (t/h)
- Product Type*.
- Saleable Aggregate Product Name*.
- Saleable Aggregates Processed*. (t)
- Running Time (Average). (h)
- Actual operation Time (Average). (h)
- Lack of Feed Time (Average). (h)
- Utilisation Index Aggregates. (%)
- Production Rate Index Aggregates. (%)
- Actual Production Rate. (t/h)
- Net Availability Index. (%)
- Running equipment effectiveness. (%)

Minimum data are indicated with a star (*), other data are automatically calculated.

The IQS user can sort and filter this list according to this different data.

In rare cases, two manual actions (add, update) will allow the user to create or update system data in order to enable the consolidation of sales data.

4.1.2.1.2 CDMP Back-end

From the different menus of the CDMP, the list of published Api (~~Table 1~~^{Table 4}) is accessible from the « Swagger » button, which allow authenticated user to perform first test.

Table 1: List of the main generic REST APIs available via Swagger

Name	Description
Archive APIs	These APIs are used to download shared data archives or files identified by their uuid and/or id.
Metadata APIs	These APIs are used to retrieve or delete all or part of shared data or files filtered and/or identified by their uuid, the site or the process.
Tasks APIs	These APIs are used to retrieve all or part of tasks identified by their uuid.
Quarry process API	This API is used for the shared data builder tool, to retrieve the quarry process dedicated to each quarry (for Akkodis internal usage only).
Upload API	This API is used to upload a shared data archive.
Log APIs	These APIs are used to retrieve logs of the current date.
Browser APIs	These APIs are used for data lake browsing.
Container controller APIs	These APIs are used for the management of the data lake containers.

The documentation related to these APIs is available directly from Swagger interface; these figures below show the list of some available endpoints (examples for “Metadata”, “Browser” and “Container controller”):

The screenshot shows the Swagger UI for the 'Metadata' API, which is used for shared data metadata management. The interface lists several endpoints with their respective HTTP methods and security requirements:

- GET** /metadata
- POST** /metadata
- DELETE** /metadata/{id}
- GET** /metadata/{uuid}
- GET** /metadata/{uuid}/files-description
- GET** /metadata/{uuid}/files-description/{id}
- DELETE** /metadata/{uuid}/metadatatask
- GET** /metadata/{uuid}/process
- GET** /metadata/{uuid}/site
- GET** /metadata/schema

Figure 27: Examples of Swagger screens showing the list of some available endpoints (“Metadata”, “Browser” and “Container controller” REST APIs).

4.1.2.1.3 Shared Data Builder application

To enable quarry users or any users lacking software development skills to use REST APIs or proxies, the IQS provides the Shared Data Builder. This tool is a Java application with a user-friendly graphical interface, as shown in figures below, that can be used on any type of computer (PC). It is a convenient and useful software which permits to access CDMP platform without any effort.

The Shared Data Builder application primarily facilitates the following functions:

- Allowing a user to input its credentials.
- Enabling a user to choose files from their local storage for inclusion in an archive (zipped) file.
- Generating the metadata file.
- Uploading the created archive file to the CDMP platform.

Figure 28: Shared Data Builder Application – “Login” screen.

Figure 29: Shared Data Builder Application – “Menu” screen.

Figure 30: Shared Data Builder Application – “Upload Shared Data” screen.

The following diagram shows the activities done by the Shared Data Builder application within its function “Build and upload” available on the main menu screen.

4.1.2.1.4 Generic connectors or proxies

To facilitate the integration of IQS (CDMP) and maximize the usage of available data, several tools called 'connectors or proxies' developed in python have been developed by Akkodis and shared with all partners in private Git repositories. Any external system (expert system) of the IQS can now automatically operate all the REST APIs described above through the following proxies:

Table 2: List of the generic proxies (connectors).

Name	Description
deq-proxy-multiple-files	This script can be used to upload all files available in a specific folder to a pilot site CDMP.
deq-proxy-file-download	This script is used to download a file of a shared data archive, selected using filters, from a pilot site data lake.
deq-proxy-zip-download	This script is used to download a shared data archive, selected using filters, from a pilot site data lake.

4.1.2.1.5 Talend integration in the IQS

Since Talend was identified as the main integration data platform, Akkodis created several pipelines that define how to retrieve and transform data received from several data producers. Once created and tested, the pipeline is deployed in a server running talend's RunTime.

Some examples of the pipelines created by Akkodis are given in section 4.1.2.3.5, for transport data received from About expert system and in section 4.1.2.3.9, for environmental data.

The management of Talend processes has been fully integrated into the IQS as shown in the next figure to simplify process initiation and monitoring directly from the CDMP.

The figure below shows the list of the available endpoints related to the Talend Process:

Figure 32: List of the available endpoints for Talend process (Swagger screen).

4.1.2.2 Data lake interface

Besides CDMP, there are several ways to upload data, navigate in the data lake, and download data from the data lake. In the DigiEcoQuarry context, the main drawback of using Azure built-in (AzCopy, Storage Explorer, SMB protocol) or third-party (SFTP) interfaces is that there is no management of any associated metadata: data uploaded using these means won't be described in a metadata database, and to retrieve data, one must know what he is searching for. Therefore, these ways of accessing the data lake are reserved for special needs, the CDMP being the recommended way for nominal or customized usages.

4.1.2.3 Interfaces with external expert systems

To ensure the connections within the IQS between the different external expert systems and the data lakes, Akkodis has developed several data proxy systems (connectors). These proxies are external programs, coded in Python, that are run over the same platform as the expert systems. These proxies enable any data consumption, at regular time intervals, using REST APIs provided by the external expert systems. They ensure that the data is retrieved in the right format, the one expected by the data lake platform (CSV or JSON formats), by transforming the collected data and/or files if needed. Finally, these proxies send the formatted data/files to the data lake (CDMP).

Akkodis shared with the DEQ partners, according to their involvement in the five pilot sites, the necessary proxies, and their related documentation, through the web service GitHub.

The figure below presents how the integration of expert systems (for example any SCADA system) with the data lake is done.

Figure 33: IQS Integration - Focus on Generic Data Provider Proxy.

All the sub-sections below present the use cases that have been experimented within DEQ project regarding this usage of proxies.

4.1.2.3.1 Interface with Mobile crusher system developed by Metso [KTA 2.1]

In Vicat site, a data pull process is established to regularly extract data from Metso's middleware system and subsequently upload it to the data lake. The data upload process adheres to the Proxy pattern, which involves creating a description file, generating a zip file, authenticating with the IQS, and finally, uploading the data. The data can be used for the creation of dashboards in the business management tool (refer to section 4.3.2.1.5.1.)

Metso will provide a single file in XLS format containing Running Hours and Fuel Consumption data with the following details:

Date	Process running				Process stopped				Total
	Crusher on load	%	Crusher on idle	%	Crusher on load	%	Crusher on idle	%	
02.08.2017	4.80	100.0%		0.0%	0.00	0.0%	0.00	0.0%	4.80

Date	Effective fuel consumption		Non-effective fuel consumption		Total	Daily average l/h
	Litres	%	Litres	%		
02.08.2017	174.00	99.4%	1.00	0.6%	175.00	36.46

Figure 34: Example of Running Hours and Fuel Consumption data provided by Metso in excel format.

Commented [ZBEA1]: @Metso please add the unit when relevant to address Reviewer's comment

4.1.2.3.2 Interface with Mintek's simulation platform for crushing and screening optimization [KTA 2.2]

In Holcim pilot site, the crushers and screeners data from the treatment plant, can be shared with Mintek in Holcim's data lake. Mintek can retrieve this data thanks to its organization within the Pilot Site's data lake and its linked metadata, for example, by process, by sub-process or any other additional metadata. Mintek, once their analysis run on their side, can store and share with Holcim and its partners (Maestro...) its calibration and optimization records. Access to data shared by Mintek is available through generic interfaces: Front-End, REST APIs and generic proxies.

4.1.2.3.3 Interface with automation & SCADA system developed by Maestro [KTA 3.1]

The following diagram illustrates the mechanism used to connect IQS with the SCADA system developed by MAESTRO, which is utilized to control production. Maestro has established a data pull process to routinely extract data from the QProduction SCADA system and then upload this data to the data lake. Once the data transfer is complete, it is made available for use by the management tools, either directly or through the data warehouse. The data warehouse generates additional Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that are subsequently utilized by the business management tool (refer to section 4.3.2.1.1).

Figure 35: Diagram of the plant production data flow within the IQS for Holcim pilot site.

To generate plant production data, a second proxy was developed to extract the minimal data required for plant production tracking and insert this data on a Postgres SQL Database. This proxy automates the data collection process. All collected data is accessible through REST APIs. This solution avoids manual upload by Holcim for this part of the expected minimum data. This proxy is executed every day by Akkodis. Then Power BI has the ability to connect with this Postgres SQL base, compute the KPI and generate the reports (refer to section 4.3.2.1.1).

The description of the Maestro’s REST API is available in D4.1.

Access to data shared by Maestro is available through generic or dedicated interfaces: Front-End, REST APIs and generic proxies.

Figure 36: List of the available endpoints for Maestro REST APIs (Swagger screen).

4.1.2.3.4 Interface with automation & SCADA system developed by Arco [KTA 3.1]

The interface with automation & SCADA system developed by Arco in the frame of the KTA 3.1 is similar than the one defined in 4.1.2.3.3 ~~Interface with automation & SCADA system developed by Maestro [KTA 3.1]~~~~interface with automation & system developed by Maestro [KTA 3.1]~~.

Arco's data are collected and then stored within the data lakes of the pilot sites on which Arco is involved except in Holcim. In that last pilot site, Arco's weighing data is uploaded through Maestro's SCADA system.

The description of Arco's REST API is available in D4.1.

Access to data shared by Arco is available through generic interfaces: Front-End, REST APIs, as shown in figures below, and generic proxies.

Figure 37: List of the available endpoints for Arco REST API (Swagger screen).

4.1.2.3.5 Interface with Abaut analytics system [KTA 3.2]

A transport data management environment has been designed and implemented within the DEQ IQS. Regularly, Abaut, for Cemex and Cimpor pilot sites, provides automatically transport data using a dedicated REST API. These data are stored in the data lake of the sites in specific databases dedicated to transport data. The description of the transport data model is available in the D4.1. Several pipelines define how to retrieve and transform these transport data (regions, projects, machines and cycles data). Talend is used to build the pipeline as shown in the following figure.

Figure 38: Examples of data pipelines (orchestrator and transport activities) defined for About transport data with Talend.

All dimensions and facts of the Power BI data model are generated using Talend pipelines.

Once the data transfer is complete, it is made available for use by the management tools, either directly or through the data warehouse. The data warehouse generates additional Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that are subsequently utilized by the business management tool (refer to section 4.3.2.1.4). To have a complete view of Transport data (raw, aggregated), pilot site's users need to connect to Abaut's Expert System.

Access to data shared by Abaut is available through generic interfaces (Front-End, REST APIs and generic proxies) or specific interfaces as described below:

Abaut About controller	
GET	/about/machine
GET	/about/machine/{id}
GET	/about/project
GET	/about/project/{id}
GET	/about/project/{id}/transports
GET	/about/region
GET	/about/region/{id}
GET	/about/transport
GET	/about/transport/{id}
GET	/about/transport/{id}/project
POST	/about/upload

Figure 39: List of the available endpoints for Abaut REST API (Swagger screen).

4.1.2.3.6 Interface with DH&P expert system [KTA 3.3]

In CSI site, DH&P collects raw transport data every 3 seconds. A specific proxy enables these data to be uploaded to the data lake. The data upload process adheres to the Proxy pattern, which involves creating a description file, generating a zip file, authenticating with the IQS, and finally, uploading the data. The zip file contains the following JSON files provided by DH&P:

- 17038_Assets_CSI_Mammendorf_GE_210823.json
- 17038_Assets_Models_CSI_GE_210823.json
- 17038_Assets_Types_CSI_GE_210823.json
- 17038_AssetValues_CAT-374_CSI_GE_210823.json
- 17038_AssetValues_CAT-775G_CSI_GE_210823.json
- 17038_AssetValues_Volvo-FMX-500_CSI_GE_210823.json
- 17038_AssetValues_WA475_CSI_GE_210823.json
- 17038_Enums_CSI_GE_210823.json
- 17038_OEM_CSI_GE_210823.json
- 17038_Param_CAT-374_CSI_GE_210823.json
- 17038_Param_CAT-775G_CSI_GE_210823.json
- 17038_Param_Volvo-FMX-500_CSI_GE_210823.json
- 17038_Param_WA475_CSI_GE_210823.json
- 17038_PLANT_CSI_GE_210823.json

Figure 40: List of the json files, containing transport data for CSI, provided by DH&P.

Then these transport data are stored in CSI data lake in specific databases dedicated to transport data. The data can be used, either directly or through the data warehouse, for the creation of KPIs and dashboards in the business management tool (refer to section 4.3.2.1.4).

The data lake provides REST APIs to enable partners accessing the DH&P data for CSI:

Assets controller <small>Assets browsing</small>		^
GET	/assets/{id}	▼ 🔒
GET	/assets/date/{date}	▼ 🔒
GET	/assets/name/{name}	▼ 🔒
GET	/assets/pageable	▼ 🔒
Assets Params controller <small>Assets params browsing</small>		^
GET	/assets/params/{id}	▼ 🔒
GET	/assets/params/date/{date}	▼ 🔒
GET	/assets/params/name/{name}	▼ 🔒
GET	/assets/params/pageable	▼ 🔒
Assets values controller <small>Assets values browsing</small>		^
GET	/assets/values/id/{assetId}/date/{date}/paramdefid/{paramDefId}	▼ 🔒
GET	/assets/values/id/{assetId}/date/{date}/paramname/{paramName}	▼ 🔒
GET	/assets/values/id/{id}/date/{date}	▼ 🔒
POST	/assets/values/id/date/ids	▼ 🔒
POST	/assets/values/id/date/names	▼ 🔒
OEM controller <small>OEM browsing</small>		^
GET	/oem/{id}	▼ 🔒
GET	/oem/name/{name}	▼ 🔒
GET	/oem/pageable	▼ 🔒
Upload controller <small>Data zip uploading</small>		^
POST	/upload/zip	▼ 🔒
POST	/upload/zip/withoutValues	▼ 🔒
DHP Service <small>DHP upload controller</small>		^
POST	/dhp/upload	▼ 🔒

Figure 41: List of the available endpoints for DH&P REST API (Swagger screen)

4.1.2.3.7 Interface with BIM and AI services [KTA 4.1/4.2]

Akkodis provided proxies to upload and download data.

- APP uploads in the data lake the following files for each pilot site:
 - ifc and rvt files are uploaded once (at the initialization).
 - xml files will be updated and uploaded on a yearly basis.
 - Cobie files will be uploaded on a weekly or monthly basis according to the updates done.
- SIGMA uploads relevant following files in the data lake according to AI services deployed in each pilot site:

Table 3: List of the files/data that can be shared by Sigma in the pilot sites data lakes.

Pilot site	AI Services	Examples of files
Cimpor	Consumption and Production Forecasting	1.-Internal data from PS (monthly) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water consumption Energy consumption (fuel, electricity, explosives) Energy costs Production 2.-External data from IPMA (monthly) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Temperature Rainfall Wind speed & direction
Vicat	Metaquarry	Documents
Holcim	Acoustic anomaly detection for mechanical failures	Records of sound and vibrations from conveyor belts and screens
Cemex	Quality estimation (based in colorimetry and granulometry)	Photos (png)
CSI	Stockpile volume calculation	Photos (jpg)

4.1.2.3.8 Interfaces with quarry’s expert system for plant production data [KTA 4.4]

A Production Data Management environment has been designed and implemented within the DEQ IQS.

Each day, the sites provide plant production, plant consumption and REE data. These data are collected either manually or automatically (as described in section 4.1.2.3.3 for Holcim using Maestro’s SCADA data), according to the configuration of the information system of the sites.

Table 4: Common data formats for the collection of the minimum plant production, plant consumption and REE data.

Plant Production	Plant Consumption	REE
<pre>{ "productType": "Roules", "productName": "0/4 MRL", "date": "2023-02-01", "startProduction": "2023-02-01T07:00:00", "endProduction": "2023-02-01T19:00:00", "downTime": 0, "productionMass": 2082, "consentedTime": 14, "totalTime": 12, "plannedMaintenanceTime": 0, "underLoadTime": 2, "lackOffFeedTime": 1, "capacity": 458, "scheduledHours": "NaN", "operatingTime": "NaN", "realProductionHours": "NaN", "netTime": "NaN", "AAR": "NaN", "efficiencyRate": "NaN", "performanceFactor": "NaN", "performanceRate": "NaN", "runningRate": "NaN", "strategicRate": "NaN", "utilizationFactor": "NaN", "requisitionRate": "NaN", "availability": "NaN", "feedingIndicator": "NaN" }</pre>	<pre>{ "consumptionDate": "2023-02-01", "fuel": 283, "diesel": 88, "energy": 481, "waterUsedForMiningWorks": 709, "primaryFreshWater": 863, "recycledWater": 250, "totalProducedTons": 2744, "totalWater": "NaN", "fuelConsumptionPerTonProcessed": "NaN", "dieselConsumptionPerTonProcessed": "NaN", "energyConsumptionPerTonProcessed": "NaN", "totalWaterConsumptionPerTonProcessed": "NaN" }, { "consumptionDate": "2023-02-02", "fuel": 69, "diesel": 100, "energy": 6412, "waterUsedForMiningWorks": 487, "primaryFreshWater": 907, "recycledWater": 352, "totalProducedTons": 2728, "totalWater": "NaN", "fuelConsumptionPerTonProcessed": "NaN", "dieselConsumptionPerTonProcessed": "NaN", "energyConsumptionPerTonProcessed": "NaN", "totalWaterConsumptionPerTonProcessed": "NaN" }, { "consumptionDate": "2023-02-03", "fuel": 56,</pre>	<pre>{ "saleDate": "2023-02-01", "bestDemonstratedPractice": 580, "productType": "Roules", "saleableAggregateProductName": "SABLE 0/4 MRL", "saleableAggregatesProcessed": 3487, "actualOperationTimeAverage": 12, "lackOffFeedTimeAverage": 0, "runningTimeAverage": 12, "utilizationIndexAggregates": "NaN", "productionRateIndexAggregates": "NaN", "actualProductionRate": "NaN", "netAvailabilityIndexAggregates": "NaN", "runningEquipmentEffectiveness": "NaN" }, { "saleDate": "2023-02-02", "bestDemonstratedPractice": 580, "productType": "Concasses", "saleableAggregateProductName": "GRAVE 0/20 MIXTE CONCASSEE", "saleableAggregatesProcessed": 743, "actualOperationTimeAverage": 12, "lackOffFeedTimeAverage": 2, "runningTimeAverage": 10, "utilizationIndexAggregates": "NaN", "productionRateIndexAggregates": "NaN", "actualProductionRate": "NaN", "netAvailabilityIndexAggregates": "NaN", "runningEquipmentEffectiveness": "NaN" }, { "saleDate": "2023-02-03",</pre>

Pilot sites are invited to complete an excel template (figure above) or extract, from their expert systems, this data according to these defined formats then run the “deq-proxy-production-consumption-ree” proxy which upload the files to the data lakes (Excel or Json files; the proxy can convert Excel_To_JSON files).

The Data Lakes of the sites ingest and store the data in specific production databases and then provide REST APIs to access the data, as presented below:

Plant consumption <small>Controllers related to the consumption</small>	
GET	/plant_consumption
GET	/plant_consumption/{id}
DELETE	/plant_consumption/{id}
DELETE	/plant_consumption/deleteAll
POST	/plant_consumption/save
POST	/plant_consumption/saveAll
POST	/plant_consumption/search
PUT	/plant_consumption/update/{id}
Plant production <small>Controllers related to the production</small>	
GET	/plant_production
POST	/plant_production/
GET	/plant_production/{id}
PUT	/plant_production/{id}
DELETE	/plant_production/{id}
GET	/plant_production/production/date/{date}
POST	/plant_production/saveAll
POST	/plant_production/search
Product types <small>Get the list of the types of products</small>	
GET	/product_types/
REE <small>Controllers related to running equipment effectiveness</small>	
GET	/ree
GET	/ree/{id}
DELETE	/ree/{id}
DELETE	/ree/deleteAll
POST	/ree/save
POST	/ree/saveAll
POST	/ree/search
PUT	/ree/update/{id}

Figure 42: List of the available endpoints for plant production, plant consumption and REE REST API (Swagger screen).

These data are made available to relevant data consumers, such as the Management Tools, for sharing. In Power BI, Akkodis implemented dashboards including plant production, plant consumption and running equipment effectiveness (REE) KPIs (refer to section 4.3.2.1 for details).

4.1.2.3.9 Interfaces with applications for environmental impact minimisation [KTA 6]

An Environmental Data Management (EDM) has been designed and implemented within the DEQ IQS according to the needs identified by Chalmers and Roctim in WP5 and documented in D5.4.

Figure 43 : Diagram of the environmental data flow within the IQS.

Each month, the sites provide plant production (mass produced in tons) and consumables (fuel, water, energy etc...) data. The plant production data can be collected either manually or automatically, when possible, according to the configuration of the information system of the sites (as described in sections 4.1.2.3.8 and 4.1.2.3.3). The consumables and allocation matrix data (fuel, water, energy etc...) can also be manually/semi-automatically collected and uploaded using a dedicated excel template (figure below) and a REST API. For example, pilot sites are invited to complete an excel template (figure above) or extract, from their expert systems, this data according to a defined format and then they run the "deq-proxy-upload-consumable" which uploads the excel template files to the data lakes (Excel or Json files; the proxy can convert Excel_To_JSON files).

ENVIRONMENT					
CONSUMABLES (Total/Month)			ALLOCATION PER MODULES (%)		
Consumable Name	Value	Unit	A1	A2	A3
Mixed waste					
Electric Energy					
Oil					
Chemicals					
AdBlue					
Flocculants					
Salt					
Rubber					
Metal					
Water					
Plastic					
Wood					
Hazardous waste					
Diesel					
Explosives					
Inert rock waste					

```

{
  "inputdata": {
    "date": "2023-07",
    "consumable": [ ... ], // 16 items
    "module": [ ... ], // 3 items
    "allocationMatrixModule": [ ... ] // 3 items
  }
}

```

Figure 44: Illustration of the data format expected to upload the consumables data.

- Then, these data are stored in the data lakes of the sites in specific databases dedicated to plant production and to environmental data. A data model has been defined to manage all functional constraints and those related to the data models of inputs and outputs. **Please zoom up to 500% to have a more readable image.**

Figure 45 : Diagram of the environmental database data model.

These data are made available to relevant data consumers, such as Roctim, for sharing.

Roctim can automatically retrieve these relevant needed data (plant production, consumables and allocation matrix data) thanks to a dedicated interface between the IQS and Plantsmith (data retrieval interface of all environmental data, REST API for the download of production and consumables data).

Once these data processed within Plantsmith, Roctim can automatically upload the corresponding EPD results and LCA reports, using the dedicated interface with the IQS (REST API for the upload of LCA/EPD results) These data are stored in the data lakes of the sites in specific databases dedicated to the EPD results.

Figure 46: List of the available endpoints for EDM REST APIs (Swagger screen).

Akkodis created several pipelines that define how to retrieve and transform consumable and EPD results data received from pilot sites and PlantSmith (Roctim expert system). Talend is used to build the pipeline as shown in the following figure. Once created and tested, the pipelines have been deployed. As an example, the following figure shows how EPD results fact table is generated using Talend job.

Figure 47: Examples of data pipelines (orchestrator, consumables assignment modules and EPD results) defined for the environmental data management with Talend.

All dimensions and facts of the Power BI data model are generated using Talend pipelines.

Finally, all these environmental data are automatically retrieved by the Environmental Management Tool (thanks to the REST API to download EPD results) to produce Environmental KPIs and dashboards (refer to section 4.3.2.2 for details on the EMT).

4.2 IoT platform

The development of the IoT platform for IQS involved designing the solution and configuring the necessary IoT components to build generic applications and IoT scenarios.

Here is a global view of the components used to build the IQS IoT platform and Business Intelligence solution:

Figure 48: Diagram of the components implemented in the IoT platform.

DigiEcoQuarry experimented two IoT use cases leveraging IoT technologies:

The first use case, related to Dust and Water monitoring at Agrepor-Cimpdor pilot site with the partner Sigma. Sigma is deploying dust (and water) counter sensors that generate data. This data is collected and stored in the DEQ IoT platform and then Sigma uses it to feed and validate the Forecast AI Service.

In the depicted scenario, multiple sensors deployed using LoRa technology are connected to a gateway. This gateway links to The Things Network (TTN), which employs the LoRaWAN network protocol to transmit sensor data. The received data is then published to the Azure IoT platform.

The propagation of this data stream is configured using the TTN-Azure IoT integration template. Within this setup, the IoT Hub and its associated devices, the Event Hub, and the Event Grid play key roles. They facilitate data capture, storage, and sharing of sensor data. Data capture generates files in JSON and Avro formats, aggregated at specific intervals, such as every 15 minutes.

The central data management platform, through its Data Lake Browser microservice, generates a data catalog accessible via both the Data Lake Browser Front-End and the Data Lake Browser REST API. This architecture enables advanced data processing operations, including bulk and stream processing, thanks to the interfaces provided by the Event Hub and its Consumer Group Interface, as well as the Event Grid's publish-subscribe mechanism. Consequently, IoT data can be immediately accessed via a direct connection between the Event Grid and the Data Lake Browser's webhook API or between the Event Grid and any external system.

Figure 49 : Schema of the Cimpdor IoT Use Case: Deployment of dust and water counter sensors to generate data to feed and validate the Forecast AI Service.

The second IoT use case, with the partner APP, has been initiated to establish the connection between the BIM and the IoT platform to take advantage of data provided by the plant processes. A detailed description can be found in D4.5: BIM- Planning 4D for all the pilots.

4.3 Reporting and Management tools

The primary objective of our Reporting and Management tools is to provide visualization and reporting capabilities for various categories of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), combined with information available in the data lake. These KPIs can originate from expert systems, be calculated and aggregated by the data warehouse after data transfer to the data lake or generated at a later stage using PowerBI. Leveraging the PowerBI ecosystem facilitates data integration from multiple sources, including databases, remote file storage, data warehouse, Rest API, etc. This capability allows us to create indicators that span different expert systems and company functions, effectively breaking down data silos.

4.3.1 Power BI ecosystem

This section demonstrates the connection and integration of IQS with the Power BI platform, as depicted in [Figure 50: IQS Platform - Focus on PowerBI](#). It also provides a brief description of the primary Power BI features employed, as shown in [Figure 51: Power BI ecosystem and component's end users](#).

Figure 50: IQS Platform - Focus on PowerBI.

Formatted: Font: (Default) +Body (Calibri)

Formatted: Font: (Default) +Body (Calibri)

Formatted: Font: (Default) +Body (Calibri), English (United Kingdom), Check spelling and grammar

Formatted: Font: (Default) +Body (Calibri)

Formatted: Font: (Default) +Body (Calibri), English (United Kingdom)

Figure 51: Power BI ecosystem and component's end users.

In summary, Power BI Desktop is a desktop tool designed for analysts, and it serves the following purposes:

- Generating queries and datasets, importing data from a diverse range of sources.
- Establishing relationships and enhancing our data model with new measures and data formats.
- Creating, uploading, publishing, and refreshing reports.

And Power BI Service is a cloud-based platform that enables Power BI users to:

- Discover and access shared data, reports, dashboards, and other business intelligence content.
- Publish their created data, reports, dashboards, and related content.
- Seamlessly connect to both on-premises and cloud data sources with scheduled data refresh.
- Share and distribute content with authorized users, both within and outside the organization.

For more in-depth information, please refer to Microsoft Power BI Documentation².

As a recommended practice, it is advisable to manage datasets and visualization reports as two separate artifacts to ensure efficient workspace management for each user. The dataset file is responsible for creating the data model, KPIs, and establishing connections with data sources. On the other hand, the report file is linked to the dataset and focuses on creating graphical representations intended for display within the Power BI report.

² See <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/power-bi/>

4.3.2 Management tools

This section presents the results of the experimentations carried out by Akkodis for the implementation of the management tools (dashboards) with Power BI using datasets stored directly in the quarries' data lakes as well as in their data warehouse (provided by Sigma). These experimentations demonstrate the effective integration of the various expert systems and components of the IQS throughout the end-to-end quarrying business processes.

These experimentations focused mainly on the building of the Business Management Tool (KTA4.4) and the Environmental Management Tool (KTA6.2), nevertheless, such solutions can be implemented also to build the Health and Safety management tool (KTA5.2), the Social acceptance management tool (KSA7.2) and the Sustainable quarrying information management tool (KSA8.2) as soon as the related input data is shared within the data lake and/or the data warehouse by the involved data providers.

4.3.2.1 Business Management Tool – KTA4.4 (BMT)

The Business Management Tool is an environment composed of microservices, PostgreSQL databases, data models and several dashboards designed using Power BI tools accessible through Azure Power BI Services. These dashboards are presented in the sub-sections below.

The design of this BMT has been defined once a deep analysis of plant production, plant consumption and running equipment effectiveness (REE) KPIs, provided by Anefa, and discussion with pilot sites have been conducted. The result of this analysis enables Akkodis to propose a first version of common data formats and efficient ICT tools for the management of these plant production data as detailed in section 4.1.2.3.8. The common data formats defined a list of minimum data to be provided. This format is easily extensible to include additional information/KPI.

4.3.2.1.1 Plant Production dashboards

The plant production dashboards have been created by Akkodis using PowerBI tools with simulated data according to first version of minimum data/KPIs for plant production (as presented in section 4.1.2.1.1.5) , as shown in figures below.

Commented [ZBEA2]: Units added in all the figures.

Figure 52 : Examples of Plant Production dashboards using Power BI.

For example, in the dashboards shown in the figure above, the user can filter the data/KPIs to have them displayed per product type, product name, year, month and day.

The first “Production” dashboard screen shows the total of the production (in tons) and other main KPIs such as:

- The capacity that is the maximum production (in tons per hour) at which the plant is designed/authorized to produce (nominal throughput).
- The average actual rate that corresponds to the total produced ton divided by the total operating hours (actual throughput).
- The real production time (average) that is the operating time reduced from the downtimes (Hours of breakdowns and stoppages).
- Several rates that compare real effective times to theoretical planned/scheduled times of the plant, for example the strategic rate corresponds to the total time the quarry is effectively operating divided by its consented time (i.e.: the total time the plant is permitted to operate).

The second “Production” dashboard screen shows the evolution of some relevant plant times during a given period compared to the total of the produced tons on the same period.

The third “Production” dashboard screen shows how the plant distributes its time among these relevant plant times (average) for a given period.

The “target rates” dashboard screen shows how the relevant rates KPIs of the quarry, for a given period, are compared to fixed thresholds and objectives.

4.3.2.1.2 Plant Consumption dashboards

The plant consumption dashboards have been created by Akkodis using PowerBi tools with simulated data according to first version of minimum data/KPIs for plant consumption (as presented in section 4.1.2.1.1.6), as shown in figures below.

DIESEL

YEAR: 2023 MONTH: Multiple se... DAY: All

WATER

YEAR: 2023 MONTH: Multiple se... DAY: All

Figure 53 : Examples of Plant Consumption dashboards using Power BI.

For example, in the dashboards shown in the figure above, the user can filter the data/KPIs to have them displayed per year, month and day.

In the first “Diesel” dashboard screen, the first graphic shows the evolution of the total diesel consumption (in liters) during a given period and the second graphic shows the evolution of the diesel consumption per produced ton (in liters/t) compared to the total of the produced tons on the same period.

In the second “Water” dashboard screen, the first graphic shows the evolution of the total water consumption (in m³), distributed per type of water origin/usage, during a given period and the second graphic shows the evolution of the water consumption per produced ton (in m³/t) compared to the total of the produced tons on the same period.

In the third “Fuel and Energy evolution” dashboard screen, the graphic compares the evolutions of the total diesel, fuel (in liters) and energy (in kW/h) consumptions during a given period.

4.3.2.1.3 Running Equipment Effectiveness dashboards

The running equipment effectiveness dashboards have been created by Akkodis using PowerBi tools with dummy data according to first version of minimum data/KPIs for REE (as presented in section 4.1.2.1.1.7).

SALEABLE AGGREGATES SUMMARY (t)

YEAR: 2023
 MONTH: All
 DAY: All

product_type	02 2023	03 2023	04 2023	05 2023	06 2023	07 2023	08 2023	09 2023	10 2023	11 2023	12 2023	Total
Concasses	12,155.00	24,226.00	15,530.00	17,995.00	16,737.00	14,143.00	21,252.00	13,079.00	14,420.00	17,147.00	15,761.00	182,445.00
GRAVE 0/20 MIXTE CONCASSEE	12,155.00	24,226.00	15,530.00	17,995.00	16,737.00	14,143.00	21,252.00	13,079.00	14,420.00	17,147.00	15,761.00	182,445.00
Roules	17,131.00	11,322.00	12,171.00	13,065.00	11,594.00	19,111.00	14,629.00	12,536.00	16,227.00	19,488.00	15,774.00	163,048.00
GRAVIER 11,2/22,4 MRL	4,438.00	2,559.00	728.00	2,364.00	1,809.00	3,281.00	3,807.00	1,355.00	3,864.00	6,981.00	2,470.00	33,656.00
GRAVILLON 4/14 MRL	2,931.00	5,021.00	8,204.00	3,413.00	3,812.00	8,511.00	8,295.00	5,466.00	4,631.00	4,763.00	4,397.00	59,444.00
SABLE 0/4 MRL	9,762.00	3,742.00	3,239.00	7,288.00	5,973.00	7,319.00	2,527.00	5,715.00	7,732.00	7,744.00	8,907.00	69,948.00
Total	29,286.00	35,548.00	27,701.00	31,060.00	28,331.00	33,254.00	35,881.00	25,615.00	30,647.00	36,635.00	31,535.00	345,493.00

SALEABLE AGGREGATES (t)

PRODUCT TYPE: All
 PRODUCT NAME: All
 YEAR: 2023
 MONTH: All
 DAY: All

SALEABLE AGGREGATES PROCESSED EVOLUTION (t)

Figure 54 : Examples of Running Equipment Effectiveness dashboards using Power BI.

For example, in the dashboards shown in the figure above, the user can filter the data/KPIs to have them displayed per saleable product type, saleable product name, year, month and day.

The first “Saleable aggregates summary” dashboard screen shows, in a table, the total sales figures (in tons) during a given period.

The second “Saleable aggregates” dashboard screen shows the evolution of the total sales (in tons), by product, during a given period.

The third “Saleable aggregates” dashboard screen shows the distribution of the sales by product type and product name in tons and in percentage during a given period.

The “Production rate” dashboard screen compares, on a given period, the actual production and the production index rates with the best demonstrated practice (BDP in t/h = the installation’s specific production capacity on aggregates production mode).

Finally, the “Running of equipment” dashboard screen represents the evolution of the Running equipment effectiveness (REE) KPIs during a given period.

To calculate these KPIs, averages (based on the two previous months) of the running, lack of feed and actual operation times have been calculated using the data stored in the plant production databases.

4.3.2.1.4 Transport dashboards

To show how the transport data can be integrated and used within the IQS, Akkodis created dashboards that use transport data provided by Abaut (as detailed in section 4.1.2.3.5) and fuel costs in the context of CIMPOR pilot site.

For fuel cost analysis, Akkodis used truck consumption (average) and fuel cost (per period) but this information could also be provided at lower frequency and extracted from the pilot site’s expert system.

The transport dashboard environment is composed of a Talend process, a PostgreSQL database, a data model and dashboards (next figures) designed using Power BI tools accessible through Azure Power Services.

Figure 55 : Examples of Transport dashboards using Power BI.

For example, in the dashboards shown in the figure above, the user can filter the data/KPIs to have them displayed per mobile machinery (types of mobile machineries: truck..., models, names, manufacturers...), locations (site names, load/unload zones), year, quarter, month and day.

These dashboards enable to display in different ways (graphics for evolutions, pie charts for distributions, tables with main figures...) and compare, per mobile machinery (truck...), locations (site names, load/unload zones), on a given period main following KPIs:

- The number of transportation cycles.
- The duration total and per cycle.
- The diesel consumption (in liters) total and per cycle.
- The costs (in €) total and per cycle.
- The driving distances (in km) total and per cycle.
- The amount of products transported (in tons) total and per cycle.

For the cycles, details per loading, driving and unloading stages can be given.

4.3.2.1.5 Other specific dashboards

4.3.2.1.5.1 Metso dashboards

As already presented in D4.1, Akkodis has relied on the Excel data provided by Metso containing information on fuel consumption of mobile crusher to be deployed in Vicat to build the following dashboard:

Figure 56: Examples of Mesto dashboards using Power BI.

Refer to the D4.1 for details on this dashboard.

4.3.2.1.5.2 Examples of dashboards connected to data warehouse sources

With Power BI, it is possible to connect to the Google Query data warehouse provided by Sigma (refer to D4.4 for details related to the DWH) using a service account and dedicated credentials. Once connected to the data warehouse, several views and/or tables are available, by pilot sites, for building specific dashboards.

At this stage of the project, the following views and/or tables are available:

Table 5: List of the views and tables available in the data warehouse for each pilot site at the stage of the project.

Vicat's tables available in the DWH	Cimpor's views and tables available in the DWH
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> vicat [3] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> allocationMatrixModule consumable module 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> cimpor [18] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> DustObservations DustObservationsFromAlenquer WeatherObservations WeatherObservationsNearAlenquer WeatherPredictions WeatherPredictionsNearAlenquer calendar dust_locations dust_observations quarries weather_locations weather_observations weather_precipitation_intensities weather_predictions weather_stations weather_types weather_wind_directions weather_wind_intensities
Holcim's views and tables available in the DWH	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Google BigQuery [2] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> bigquery-public-data nlp-big-query [4] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> cimpor [18] csi holcim [5] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> TotalProduction calendar maestro maestro_data quarries vicat 	

Here is an example of a dashboard built using data provided by the DWH for Cimpor:

Figure 57: Example of dashboard connected to the Cimpor's data warehouse using Power BI.

These graphics in this dashboard (figure above) show the evolution, on a given period, of some meteorological parameters (humidity, pressure, temperature...) to be compared to the dust emissions (by particles sizes) at the pilot site.

4.3.2.2 Environmental Management Tool – KTA6.2 (EMT)

The Environmental Management Tool is an environment composed of a microservice, a Talend process, a PostgreSQL database, a data model and two dashboards (next figures) designed using Power BI tools accessible through Azure Power Services.

Figure 58 : Home page of the Environmental Management Tool (EMT).

The first “consumable assignment” dashboards below show the consumables data collected at pilot sites levels and how these consumables are allocated by groups of products and by modules (ie by process stages):

Consumable Assignment By Module

MODULE: Multiple selections | CONSUMABLE: All | YEAR: Multiple selections | MONTH: All

Consumable data by Module							
modulecode	A1		A2		A3		Total
consumablename	moduleconsumablevalue	Unit	moduleconsumablevalue	Unit	moduleconsumablevalue	Unit	moduleconsumablevalue Unit
AdBlue	0.00	kg	0.00	kg	0.00	kg	0.00 kg
Chemicals	0.00	kg	0.00	kg	0.00	kg	0.00 kg
Diesel	67,039.20	l	603,352.80	l	0.00	l	670,392.00 l
Electrical Energy	0.00	kWh	0.00	kWh	801,540.00	kWh	801,540.00 kWh
Explosives	163,656.00	kg	0.00	kg	0.00	kg	163,656.00 kg
Flocculants	0.00	kg	0.00	kg	0.00	kg	0.00 kg
Hazardous Waste	0.00	kg	0.00	kg	6,600.00	kg	6,600.00 kg
Inert rock waste	0.00	kg	0.00	kg	81,000,000.00	kg	81,000,000.00 kg
Metal	0.00	kg	0.00	kg	204.00	kg	204.00 kg
Mixed Waste	0.00	kg	0.00	kg	4,056.00	kg	4,056.00 kg
01 2019	0.00	kg	0.00	kg	338.00	kg	338.00 kg
02 2019	0.00	kg	0.00	kg	338.00	kg	338.00 kg
03 2019	0.00	kg	0.00	kg	338.00	kg	338.00 kg
04 2019	0.00	kg	0.00	kg	338.00	kg	338.00 kg

Figure 59: Examples of consumables assignments dashboards (EMT) using Power BI.

The user can filter the data/KPIs to have them displayed per consumable and by year and month.

The second “EPD” dashboards below display the EPD results (as defined by Chalmers), including the highest environmental impacts, generated by PlantSmith expert system (tool developed by Roctim):

Potential Environmental Impact In Impact Categories For One Declared Unit Of Product Group

MODULE: Production Stage | YEAR: All | MONTH: All | DATE: All

Potential Environmental Impact In Impact Categories For One Declared Unit Of Product Group Per Lifecycle Stage

Parameter Describing Environmental Impacts	Production Stage							
	A1 Raw Material Supply				A2 Transport			
	ARMOURSTONE	CONCRETE	PRIMARY	SECONDARY	ARMOURSTONE	CONCRETE	PRIMARY	SECONDARY
ADP-fossil fuels								
MJ net calorific value	58.9786488770531	58.9786488770531	58.9786488770531	58.9786488770531	222.0390923914006	222.0390923914006	222.0390923914006	222.0390923914006
ADP-minerals & metals								
kg Sb eq.	0.0000023708805	0.0000023708805	0.0000023708805	0.0000023708805	0.0000012698634	0.0000012698634	0.0000012698634	0.0000012698634
AP								
Mol H+ eq.	0.0385794521398	0.0385794521398	0.0385794521398	0.0385794521398	0.0960561932701	0.0960561932701	0.0960561932701	0.0960561932701
EP-freshwater								
kg (PO4)3- eq.	0.0000082507623	0.0000082507623	0.0000082507623	0.0000082507623	0.0000495154015	0.0000495154015	0.0000495154015	0.0000495154015
EP-freshwater-P								
kg (P) eq.	0.0000247522870	0.0000247522870	0.0000247522870	0.0000247522870	0.0001485462046	0.0001485462046	0.0001485462046	0.0001485462046
EP-marine								
kg N eq.	0.0151614422283	0.0151614422283	0.0151614422283	0.0151614422283	0.0470424931327	0.0470424931327	0.0470424931327	0.0470424931327
EP-terrestrial								
mol N eq.	0.2005872981467	0.2005872981467	0.2005872981467	0.2005872981467	0.5206789151934	0.5206789151934	0.5206789151934	0.5206789151934
ETP-fw								
CTUe	27.2050333051144	27.2050333051144	27.2050333051144	27.2050333051144	160.4504410180962	160.4504410180962	160.4504410180962	160.4504410180962
GWP-biogenic								
kg CO2 eq.	-0.0118380504314	-0.0118380504314	-0.0118380504314	-0.0118380504314	-0.0212754840259	-0.0212754840259	-0.0212754840259	-0.0212754840259
GWP-fossil								

Highest Contributing Flow To Each Product Group Per Impact Category

YEAR: All | MONTH: January | DATE: All

Product Group	Impact Category	Highest Impact Ressource	% Total Impact
ARMOURSTONE	AP	Explosives	100.00
CONCRETE	AP	Explosives	98.90
PRIMARY	AP	Explosives	89.30
SECONDARY	AP	Explosives	80.20
ARMOURSTONE	ODP	Diesel	78.00
ARMOURSTONE	GWP-total	Diesel	77.90
CONCRETE	ODP	Diesel	77.50
CONCRETE	GWP-total	Diesel	77.40
PRIMARY	ODP	Diesel	72.20
PRIMARY	GWP-total	Diesel	72.10
ARMOURSTONE	EP-terrestrial	Diesel	69.90
CONCRETE	EP-terrestrial	Diesel	69.80
PRIMARY	EP-terrestrial	Diesel	68.90
ARMOURSTONE	EP-freshwater	Diesel	68.70
CONCRETE	EP-freshwater	Diesel	68.50
SECONDARY	EP-terrestrial	Diesel	67.80
SECONDARY	ODP	Diesel	66.80

Figure 60: Examples of EPD results dashboards (EMT) using Power BI.

The user can filter the data/KPIs to have them displayed by year and by month.

4.3.3 Power BI Dashboards deployment

In the context of a specific site, all the dashboards created can be shared directly or included in a Power-Bi Application. The chosen solution will be defined by the pilot site. However, the organisation of the dashboards is constrained by the rules and the development process recommended by Power-Bi. Hence a dashboard must be defined in a dedicated workspace accessible to dashboard’s editors and should be dedicated to a specific topic or function (Environmental data, production, transport) Then, the aggregation of multiple dashboards can be performed in a power-bi, application accessible to all pilot sites or managers.

The following figure shows an example of an application that includes six dashboards. Each one contains its visualizations:

Figure 61: Examples of Power BI App (DEQ App for Cimpor).

The organization of dashboard by topics and in application will enable the deployment of CI/CD process needed for the deployment of efficient management tools.

4.4 IQS deployment diagram

In this section, a detailed deployment diagram of the Intelligent Quarrying System (IQS) is presented. This diagram provides a comprehensive overview of the system's architecture, outlining how various components and services are distributed across different layers and environments. Understanding the deployment structure is essential to grasp the system's scalability, reliability, and interactions among its components.

Figure 62: Diagram for the DEQ IQS deployment.

This diagram represents the deployment for one pilot site.

In our architecture, Azure VMs are configured with standard sizes to meet the requirements of various components within the system. Specifically:

CDMP and Database Nodes: We utilize Azure B4ms VMs, which are equipped with 4 virtual CPUs (vCPU) and 16 GB of RAM. These VMs are chosen for their robust computing power and memory capacity, making them well-suited for the tasks associated with our CDMP and Database nodes.

Keycloak and Talend Nodes: For Keycloak and Talend nodes, we opt for Azure B2ms VMs. These VMs feature 2 vCPUs and 8 GB of RAM, providing a balanced and efficient configuration to handle the responsibilities of these components.

In our system, all services and communication channels are meticulously secured. To ensure data integrity and confidentiality, we employ Let's Encrypt certificates to authenticate all services and encrypt communication. This means that every interaction within our system takes place over secure HTTPS connections, providing a robust layer of security that safeguards pilot sites data and ensures the privacy of the users.

5 IQS test plan

This section describes the test activity implemented within the scope of the project.

5.1 Test strategy

The purpose of the test activity is to check and demonstrate the compliance of the IQS with the validated specifications. It is made up of the test plan, which describes the test strategy, the overall running of test activity, as well as its monitoring. The document is supplemented as the project progresses with the test descriptions and results obtained. The scope of the IQS test plan described in this section is the data lake platform, the IoT platform and the integration with the sensors and sub-platforms on the field as well as the integration with the BIM, AI, Data warehouse, Power BI Platform and other Services in the cloud, as presented in the previous section 4.

The process of the Akkodis DEQ Project team is composed by the following steps of the DevOps model:

Figure 63: DevOps processus followed by Akkodis DEQ Project team.

It is a process of continuous improvements, integration and deployment. Therefore, Akkodis DEQ Project team is also continuously testing parts of the IQS.

The test plan and strategy can be examined, supplemented and updated at each step of the process.

Following types of tests are carried out on following environments by following team members (process overview):

- Unit tests on DEVELOPMENT - LOCAL PC environment.
- Functional tests on DEVELOPMENT - VM for TEST environment.
- Integration tests on INTEGRATION.
- Validation test on INTEGRATION for PARTNERS environments.

5.2 Test environment and tools

The testing activities encompass a range of environments and tools to ensure comprehensive and effective quality assurance. The following environments are utilized throughout the testing process:

- DEVELOPMENT - LOCAL PC: This is the environment where initial testing and debugging occur. It allows for rapid iterations and immediate feedback for developers.
- DEVELOPMENT - VM for TEST: In this environment, a virtual machine is set up specifically for testing purposes. It provides a controlled and isolated space for more rigorous testing of the software.

- **INTEGRATION:** Integration testing is a crucial phase in the testing process. This environment is dedicated to testing how different components of the software work together, identifying potential integration issues and ensuring overall system compatibility.
- **INTEGRATION for PARTNERS:** As partnerships and integrations with third-party systems are essential for many applications, this environment is dedicated to testing the interactions between the software and partner systems.

To execute these testing activities effectively, a set of powerful tools are employed:

- **Python:** Python is used for various testing tasks, including test automation and scripting to streamline and enhance the testing process.
- **Eclipse IDE for Enterprise Java and Web Developers:** Eclipse provides a robust integrated development environment for Java and web development, which is instrumental in creating and executing test scripts.
- **pgAdmin4:** pgAdmin4 is utilized for database testing, enabling testers to interact with and manipulate the database during testing.
- **Postman:** Postman is a versatile tool for API testing, allowing for the creation and execution of API requests and validation of their responses.
- **PyCharm Community Edition:** PyCharm is a Python-focused integrated development environment that aids in writing and running Python test scripts.
- **Node.js:** Node.js is used for server-side testing and various backend testing tasks, enhancing the efficiency of the testing process.
- **Newman:** Newman, a part of the Postman ecosystem, is employed for running Postman collections from the command line, automating API tests.
- **Jira/X-Ray & Confluence:** Jira and Confluence are used for test management, issue tracking, and documentation. X-Ray, an extension for Jira, helps manage and execute test cases effectively.
- These environments and tools collectively ensure a rigorous and comprehensive testing process, enhancing the quality and reliability of the software under examination.

5.3 Methodology and process applied

For each type of test, run the test activity means performing the following steps:

- Prepare the test.
- Execute the test.
- Evaluate the test results.
- Close and assess the test execution.

The test activity is monitored through the Jira tool and discussed during the AKKODIS DEQ project team progress meetings.

5.3.1 Test preparation

Test preparation activities define, document and configure the tests sets to be executed in the test environment (list the tests cases, the potential pre-conditions, their steps, the needed data set, the expected results).

5.3.2 Test execution

Test execution activities are to run each test included in the list of the test's sets, following the defined steps, manually or automatically, using Postman collections, depending on the components and/or features to be tested. In parallel, during the test execution, all the test results necessary information is completed/documented (actual result, step state, evidence, defect/deviation, execution status...).

5.3.3 Test Results and test monitoring

For each type of test, thanks to the test results information collected during the test execution phase, test results reports are generated. The test execution report as shown below is used as a decision tool.

6 Conclusions

This document D4.2: "Report on IQS design and architecture" is a public deliverable done in the frame of the WP4. It describes the design and architecture of the IQS that covers the business requirements defined in D1.3-"Requirements for Quarry full digitalization (for Smart Sensors, Automation & Process Control, and for ICT solutions, BIM and AI report" and covers the ICT requirements analysis defined in D4.1-"Report on IQS ICT requirements analysis and assets inventory").

After an update of data flow in all the sites, different strategies have been defined to enable data collection, storage and sharing between the expert systems, the BIM, the Data Warehouse and the Reporting and Management Tools.

IQS building blocks

The implementation of digital solutions in the quarry processes involves the development and integration of various components. These components include:

- **Data Lakes:** These consist of tools for data management, storage in Azure cloud, forming the foundation of the IQS.
- **Application Gateway:** It serves as the Frontal Gateway for the DigiEcoQuarry Application, exposing specific REST API Web Services. When deployed in production, it incorporates features like high availability, load balancing, and firewall.
- **Keycloak:** this component is used for authenticating and authorizing users. It implements OpenID Connect and manages user information in an external PostgreSQL database.
- **Microservices:** These are deployed as a microservice-based architecture. They include download, upload, data restitution, and data ingestion microservices, each tailored to specific user requests. They are responsible for retrieving and storing uploaded files and ingesting data into specific databases.
- **Talend (ETL Tool):** Talend is used for Extraction, Transformation, and Loading (ETL) of data sets, with a focus on reading PostgreSQL databases and generating content for enriching incoming data.
- **Azure Data Storage and PostgreSQL:** IQS data files are stored in dedicated Azure blob storage containers, and PostgreSQL is used as the hierarchical database solution.

Data management tools

All these building blocks are integrated and used in the Centralized Data Management Platform (CDMP). The CDMP and its associated tools facilitate efficient data management and collaboration in quarry operations. The CDMP serves as a central platform that collects and stores data from pilot sites, enabling quarry partners to upload, browse, access, and download data. This platform relies on REST APIs and on common metadata description model agreed upon among partners. CDMP's web interface allows data sharing between partners based on defined authorizations, and for specialized requirements, low-level data lake APIs can be utilized.

The CDMP Front-End developed with Angular offers various features, including the ability to access and manage shared data, monitor data upload tasks, and track Talend processes. Additionally, it provides a Data lake browser tool for accessing data shared by external systems (IoT) and monitoring plant productions data.

The CDMP Back-end developed with spring-boot technologies offers a range of generic REST APIs for data collection, upload, and download of expert system data, along with tools for tasks such as browsing the data lake and managing data lake containers.

Furthermore, the Shared Data Builder application developed with java allows users to manually share any data with their metadata. This system streamlines data management and ensures efficient communication and access to quarry-related information.

IQS interfaces

IQS interfaces with external expert systems through the utilization of proxy patterns, allowing seamless data exchange and integration with various external systems. The key interfaces include:

- Interface with Mobile Crusher System (Metso).
- Interface with MINTEK's Simulation Platform.
- Interface with Automation & SCADA System (MAESTRO).
- Interface with Automation & SCADA System (ARCO).
- Interface with About Analytics System.
- Interface with DH&P Expert System.
- Interfaces with BIM and AI Services.
- Interfaces with Quarry's Expert System for Plant Production Data.
- Interfaces with Applications for Environmental Impact Minimization (Chalmers & Roctim).

These interfaces enhance data exchange and integration with external expert systems, contributing to the effectiveness of the IQS in managing and utilizing quarry data.

PowerBI Integration

The IQS places significant emphasis on reporting and management tools to provide comprehensive visualization and reporting capabilities for Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) across various aspects of quarry operations. These KPIs may originate from expert systems, be calculated and aggregated within the data warehouse, or generated later using Power BI, allowing data integration from various sources and breaking down data silos effectively.

The IQS is seamlessly integrated with the Power BI ecosystem, enabling the visualization and analysis of data. The IQS demonstrates its ability to effectively integrate various expert systems and components throughout the quarrying business processes. Several reports including Plant production, Plant consumption, REE, Transport, Mobile crusher, Environmental show case this integration.

Finally, the test section presents a thorough testing strategy, outlining environments, tools, and processes to ensure IQS quality platform in the DigiEcoQuarry project.

7 References

- D1.3: Requirements for Quarry full digitalization (for Smart Sensors, Automation & Process Control, and for ICT solutions, BIM and AI report)
- D4.1: Report on IQS ICT requirement analysis.
- D4.4: Report on Architecture of the data Warehouse and its integration.
- D4.5: BIM- Planning 4D for all the pilots.
- D5.4: Pre-verified Environmental Product Declaration documentation for pilot plant based on historical data.
- D7.1: Context narrative, social risk matrix and Stakeholder Mapping.
- D7.2: Social Risk Analysis

List of Figures

Figure 1: Cemex 's Data Flow Diagram.....	12
Figure 2: Vicat's Data Flow Diagram.....	13
Figure 3: Holcim's Data Flow Diagram.....	14
Figure 4: Agrepor Cimpor' s Data Flow Diagram.....	15
Figure 5: CSI's Data Flow Diagram.....	16
Figure 6: Data Lake architecture components view.....	17
Figure 7 Frontal Gateway	17
Figure 8 Keycloak.....	18
Figure 9 Microservices.....	19
Figure 10 Taletn ETL tool.....	19
Figure 11 File Dropper.....	20
Figure 12 Azure Data Storage.....	20
Figure 13: CDMP general architecture.....	21
Figure 14: CDMP Front-End: Welcome page – “Home” screen.....	22
Figure 15: CDMP Front-End – “Shared Data” screen.	22
Figure 16: CDMP Front-End – “Summary of selected ítems”(Shared data) screen.....	23
Figure 17: CDMP Front-End – “Details” (Shared data) screen.....	23
Figure 18: CDMP Front-End – “Files available” (Shared data) screen.....	24
Figure 19: CDMP Front-End – “Shared Data Task” screen.....	25
Figure 20: CDMP Front-End – “Talent Process” screen.	25
Figure 21: CDMP Front-End – “Data lake Browser” screen.....	26
Figure 22: CDMP Front-End – “Summary of selected items”(Data lake Browser) screen.	27
Figure 23: CDMP Front-End – “Details”(Data lake Browser) screen.....	27
Figure 24: CDMP Front-End – “Plant Production” screen.....	28
Figure 25: CDMP Front-End – “Plant Consumption” screen.....	29
Figure 26: CDMP Front-End – “REE” screen (Running Equipment Effectiveness)	30
Figure 27: Examples of Swagger screens showing the list of some available endpoints (“Metadata”, “Browser” and “Container controller” REST APIs).....	32
Figure 28: Shared Data Builder Application – “Login” screen.....	33
Figure 29: Shared Data Builder Application – “Menu” screen.....	33
Figure 30: Shared Data Builder Application – “Upload Shared Data” screen.....	33
Figure 31: Activity Diagram “Build and Upload” (Shared data builder application).....	34
Figure 32: List of the available endpoints for Talend process (Swagger screen).....	35
Figure 33: IQS Integration - Focus on Generic Data Provider Proxy.....	36

Figure 34: Example of Running Hours and Fuel Consumption data provided by Metso in excel format.....37

Figure 35: Diagram of the plant production data flow within the IQS for Holcim pilot site.38

Figure 36: List of the available endpoints for Maestro REST APIs (Swagger screen).....38

Figure 37: List of the available endpoints for Arco REST API (Swagger screen).....39

Figure 38: Examples of data pipelines (orchestrator and transport activities) defined for Abaut transport data with Talend.41

Figure 39: List of the available endpoints for Abaut REST API (Swagger screen)42

Figure 40: List of the json files, containing transport data for CSI, provided by DH&P.42

Figure 41: List of the available endpoints for DH&P REST API (Swagger screen).....43

Figure 42: List of the available endpoints for plant production, plant consumption and REE REST API (Swagger screen).45

Figure 43 : Diagram of the environmental data flow within the IQS.....46

Figure 44: Illustration of the data format expected to upload the consumables data46

Figure 45 : Diagram of the environmental database data model.....47

Figure 46: List of the available endpoints for EDM REST APIs (Swagger screen).....48

Figure 47: Examples of data pipelines (orchestrator, consumables assignation modules and EPD results) defined for the environmental data management with Talend50

Figure 48: Diagram of the components implemented in the IoT platform.....51

Figure 49 : Schema of the Cimpor IoT Use Case: Deployment of dust and water counter sensors to generate data to feed and validate the Forecast AI Service.52

Figure 50: IQS Platform - Focus on PowerBI.....53

Figure 51: Power BI ecosystem and component’s end users.54

Figure 52 : Examples of Plant Production dashboards using Power BI.....57

Figure 53 : Examples of Plant Consumption dashboards using Power BI.....59

Figure 54 : Examples of Running Equipment Effectiveness dashboards using Power BI.....62

Figure 55 : Examples of Transport dashboards using Power BI.....67

Figure 56: Examples of Mesto dashboards using Power BI68

Figure 57 : Example of dashboard connected to the Cimpor’s data warehouse using Power BI.....69

Figure 58 : Home page of the Environmental Management Tool (EMT).....70

Figure 59: Examples of consumables assignations dashboards (EMT) using Power BI.....72

Figure 60: Examples of EPD results dashboards (EMT) using Power BI.73

Figure 61: Examples of Power BI App (DEQ App for Cimpor).....74

Figure 62: Diagram for the DEQ IQS deployment.....75

Figure 63: DevOps process followed by Akkodis DEQ Project team.77

Figure 64: Example of “Test Executions Report”79

Figure 65: Example of “Test Runs Report”79

List of Tables

Table 1: List of the main generic REST APIs available via Swagger.....	31
Table 2: List of the generic proxies (connectors).....	35
Table 3: List of the files/data that can be shared by Sigma in the pilot sites data lakes.....	44
Table 4: Common data formats for the collection of the minimum plant production, plant consumption and REE data.....	44
Table 5: List of the views and tables available in the data warehouse for each pilot site at the stage of the project.....	69

